

Investigation of uncertainties and sensitivity of CORDEB CP7-02 test calculation with ASTECv3.1.1/SUNSET

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ABSTRACT

Often in case of severe accidents at NPP the reactor core could be overheated, which leads to core degradation, melting of reactor fuel and in-vessel internal structures, and corium relocation into the lower head of the reactor vessel. That's why it is very important to understand the behavior of the molten corium pool into the lower vessel plenum. Many experiments have been done to investigate this behavior.

The presented hereafter analysis has been done by INRNE-BAS and simulates the CORDEB2 CP7-02 experiment, with ASTECv3.1.1 severe accident computer code. The experiment is devoted to the investigation of oxide-metal corium pool thermochemistry and stratification. The experiment has been proposed in the frame of In-Vessel Melt Retention (IVMR) project H2020.

The results from the simulation with ASTECv3.1.1 code show that the code predicts the occurrence of three corium layers: a light metal layer at the top, an oxide layer in the middle, and a heavy metal layer at the bottom. The calculated by ASTECv3.1.1 masses and the compositions of the layers correspond reasonably with the data received from CORDEB2 CP7-02 experiment. This also validates the ASTECv3.1.1 ability to simulate the late phase of a severe accidents.

After that, there have been done uncertainty and sensitivity analyses by SUNSET statistical computational tool of ASTEC to account the influence of three basic input parameters on the kinetics of stratification and on the final masses of the stratified phases.

Keywords CORDEB2 CP7-02 experiment, ASTECv3.1.1 code, SUNSET, corium stratification, corium thermochemistry, uncertainties, sensitivity

1. INTRODUCTION

The CORDEB2 CP7-02 experiment with a prototypical corium was performed on the RASPLAV-3 facility at NITI (Russia), [1, 2]. The experiment was conducted by IRSN, CEA, EDF, and Framatome. The CORDEB2 CP7-02 experiment was proposed and co-funded at EU IVMR project [3, 4].

The INRNE-BAS has simulated the CORDEB2 CP7-02 experiment by ASTECv3.1.1 version. The experiment investigates two layers of sub-oxidized corium pool in the cold crucible with an inside diameter of 7 cm. After crust formation at the top of the molten pool a molten stainless steel is poured onto the crust. This additional steel interacts with the crust [5, 6] and the pool below leading to three-layer stratification of the pool [7]. The ASTECv3.1.1 code predicts occurrence of three corium layers: light metal layer at the top, oxide layer in the middle and heavy metal layer at the bottom. The calculated by ASTECv3.1.1 masses and compositions of the layers have been compared with data received from CORDEB2 CP7-02 experiment [8].

The compositions of the layers have been compared with data received from the post experimental analyses of the post-mortem ingot.

Initially, the molten pool was produced from the interaction of two species: 2.15 kg of sub-oxidized corium and 0.43 kg of stainless steel. The mass of the steel is 20% with respect of the mass of the oxide. These two species have been poured in the cold crucible with diameter 7 cm and have been heated by induction till reaching temperature ($T_{\text{pool}} \approx 2590^\circ\text{C}$). As a result, the pool stratifies in two layers: an oxide layer at the top and a heavier metallic layer at the bottom. [7]. The crust is formed at the top of the molten pool by freezing. A molten stainless steel with temperature 2600°C is poured onto the crust. The mass of this steel is 15% with respect of the mass of the initial oxide. After the molten steel pouring the experiment continues 6 hours. During the experiment it has been supported upper surface temperature of 1900°C .

Initial compositions of species in the beginning of experiment:

- Initial oxide (2,15 kg) consists of UO_2 (76,2 %), Zr (15,1 %) and ZrO_2 (8,7 %)
- Initial heavy metal (0,431 kg) consists of Fe (74,22 %), Cr (16,75 %) and Ni (9,03 %)
- Slump of stainless steel (0,329 kg) consists of Fe (74,22 %), Cr (16,75 %) and Ni (9,03 %)

The experimental results from the post-mortem ingot (Figure 1) show: light metal at the top (1), oxide crust (2), light metal (LM) below the oxide crust (3), oxide (6), heavy metal (HM) in the middle of the oxide (4) and HM layer at the bottom of the crucible, below the oxide (5).

Figure 1. Vertical cross-section of the CORDEB2 CP7-02 post-mortem ingot [2]

At the end of the experiment, a large amount of light metals is observed. This indicates that a significant part of the building elements of the heavy metals has moved into the layers of light metals. At the end of experiment, it could be seen repartitioning of species. The amount of U and Zr in the light metal increases. The thickness of the initial HM layer decreases but the thickness of the LM layer increases. The result compositions from the post-mortem ingot analyses are presented in Figure 1 and Table I, where:

- W_U is the mass fraction of U (%) in the corresponding phase;
- W_{Zr} is the mass fraction of Zr (%) in the corresponding phase;
- $W_{\text{Fe,Cr,Ni}}$ is the mass fraction of STEEL (%) in the corresponding phase;
- W_O is the mass fraction of O (%) in the corresponding phase.

Table I. Compositions of phases evaluated from the experimental results at the end of experiment.

Phase	Mass (kg)	W_U	W_Z	$W_{\text{Fe,Cr,Ni}}$	W_O
(LM) Top metal (1)	0.32 kg	29%	11.5%	58.5%	1.0%

(LM) Metal 1 (3)	0.86 kg	22.4%	10.4%	65.60%	1.6%
(HM) Metal 2 (4)	0.08 kg	26.9%	13.7%	57.8%	1.6%
(HM) Metal 3 (5)	0.11 kg	27%	17.6%	53.9%	1.5%
Oxide (6)	1.42 kg (including crust (2))	64.9%	22.1%	0.3%	12.6%
Oxide crust (2)	Not evaluated	64.5%	11.7%	13.8%	10%

For the need of comparison with results from ASTEC code, the masses of the LM phases and the masses of HM phases in Table I have been summed. The corresponding fractions of the main components in the metal layers are interpolated. In this case the Table I was transformed in Table II.

Table II: Transformed table of the experimental masses and element compositions at the end of experiment.

Phase α	Mass (kg)	W_U	W_{Zr}	$W_{Fe,Cr,Ni}$	W_O
Light metal	1.18 kg	$\approx 29\%$	$\approx 11\%$	$\approx 58\%$	$\approx 1\%$
Oxide	1.42 kg (including crust)	$\approx 65\%$	$\approx 22\%$	$\approx 0.3\%$	$\approx 13\%$
Heavy metal	0.19 kg	$\approx 27\%$	$\approx 14\%$	$\approx 57\%$	$\approx 1.5\%$

2. BRIEF DESCRIPTION OF THE ASTEC INPUT FOR THE CORDEB2 CP7-02 EXPERIMENT

A stand-alone calculation has been performed with ICARE and CESAR modules of ASTECv3.1.1 computer code. Initially it has been modelled a crucible and corium in it (Fig. 2). ICARE module of ASTEC is used to compute the thermo-chemical behavior in the of corium in the crucible. CESAR module defines the thermal-hydraulics in the channel of crucible.

Figure 2. Crucible shape and the corium in it in the beginning of the transient

The crucible has inside diameter 7 cm. It has been modelled from a fictive material with very low Λ [0.2 W/(m²K)]. Practically there is no heat transfer between the crucible and the corium. The corium is composed of UO₂, ZrO₂, Zr, and Steel (Fe, Cr and Ni). Initially it has been modelled as a two-phase stratified corium (heavy metal layer at the bottom and oxide layer at the top) at liquid state, with temperature 2590 °C. In the ASTEC calculation an upper crust (8 mm) occurs above the oxide in the first seconds of transient. (at the top of the oxide layer). Molten stainless steel is poured onto the crust. The crust has been melted in a few seconds after the second part of molten steel is added at the top. Then, the transient prolongs 6 h (21600 sec). During the transient it has been supported upper corium boundary temperature of 1900 °C.

Initial compositions and temperatures of the both layers and the second part of steel that was poured later on the oxide crust are modeled according to the specifications of the experiment [2, 8] (Table III).

During the transient the both layers are supported to be in liquid state so that there will be thermal-chemical interactions between them.

Table III. Initial elements composition in the layers and second slump composition in ASTEC

Phase α	mass (kg)	W_U	W_{Zr}	$W_{Fe,Cr,Ni}$	W_{Fe}	W_{Cr}	W_{Ni}
Stainless steel first pouring	0.431 kg	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	74.22%	16.75%	9.03%
Oxide	2.15 kg	76.2%	15.1%	8.7%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
Stainless steel second pouring	0.329 kg	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	74.22%	16.75%	9.03%

The upper outside temperature was simulated in ASTEC by $T_{PLATE} = 1900\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (2173 K). T_{PLATE} is a fictitious margin, which is used for simulation of a core support plate in a real reactor in ASTEC.

During the transient, in the first 10 sec. an upper crust with thickness of approximately 8 mm occurs on the top of the corium (see Fig.4). The second slump of stainless steel (0.329 kg) with temperature of $2600\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ starts at 10 sec. After that moment the calculation has been prolonged to 6h (till 21610 sec). Slump is organized as a flow that starts from 10 sec to 25 sec (continues 15 sec). The mass flow of the stainless-steel slump is 0.02193333 kg/s . In the ASTEC input model it was chosen option that defined possibility for three layers stratification and allows the thermo-chemical interactions in the pool [7]. Power insert is enough to support liquid fraction of approximately 0.8 in the oxide layer. The results from the ASTECv3.1.1 calculation have been compared with the experimental values pointed in Table II.

3. RESULTS FROM THE CORDEB2 CP7-02 SIMULATION WITH ASTECV3.1.1 COMPUTER CODE

Figure 3. Crucible shape and the corium in it at the end of the transient

Colored scheme of the crucible and the stratified pool in it at the end of the experiment, computed by ASTECv3.1.1 computer code is presented in Figure 3. As it seen from the figure the two-layered pool configuration has been transformed in three-layered pool formation.

In Figure 4 it is shown the oxidic crust appearance in the beginning of the transient. Pouring of melted stainless steel at 10 sec leads to assimilation of the oxidic crust in the new born light metal (LM). Further, the molten steel continues to interact with the layers below the crust. Due to the thermo-chemical interactions in the pool and due to the movement of species pool stratifies in three layers: light metal layer at the top, oxide layer in the middle and heavy metal layer at the bottom (see Figure 5).

Figure 4. Crust above the oxide layer in the first 10 sec of transient

The evolution of the mass of the formatted three pool layers is presented at Figure 5. It could be seen that during the transient time the thickness of LM layer increases but the thickness of HM layer decreases. The molten steel poured above the oxide interacts with the layers below and the spices received have been assimilated in the different layers.

Figure 5. Mass of the layers in the crucible (MAGMA1 – HM layer, MAGMA2 – OXIDE layer, MAGMA3 – LM layer, DEBRIS1 and 2 – solid unmelted particals in the pool)

Comparison of results from the ASTECv3.1.1 computer code and from the experiment is done in the Table IV below. It has been compared the masses of layers and the mass fractions of the components in the oxide and metal layers at the end of ASTEC calculation and at the end of experiment.

Table IV. Comparison at the end of calculation (21610 sec)

Comparison at the end of calculation (21610 sec)						
	LM calc	LM exp	OX calc	OX exp	HM calc	HM exp
Mass (kg)	1.13 kg	1.18 kg	1.61 kg	1.42 kg	0.17 kg	0.19 kg
Mass fraction fU (%)	31%	≈ 29%	64%	65%	30%	≈ 27%
Mass fraction fZr (%)	10%	≈ 11%	21%	22%	12%	≈ 14%
Mass fraction fO (%)	0.7%	≈ 1%	14%	13%	0.5%	1.5%

Mass fraction						
fFe(%)+fCr(%)+fNi (%)	58%	$\approx 58\%$	0.8%	0.3%	57%	$\approx 57\%$

4. RESULTS FROM SUNSET CALCULATIONS

An uncertainty and sensitivity investigation of certain parameters have been done for the simulation of CORDEB2 CP7-02 experiment with ASTECv3.1.1/SUNSET. The investigation let us to study the uncertainties in some parameters that influence on the important output parameters. These input parameters influence on the kinetics of stratification.

The SUNSET (Statistical UNcertainty and Sensitivity Evaluation Tool) software developed by IRSN, is a statistical tool designed for uncertainty and sensitivity analysis of mathematical or physical models like computer codes. It is composed of two parts: a set of statistical computing and interface functions, based on C++ language and a Graphical User Interface allowing the call of statistical functions, in Java language.

It has been created an input for SUNSET, where the uncertain input parameters were determined and also it was pointed their possible range. After that, 100 calculation runs have been performed. The sets of the input parameters in these 100 calculations are generated by the SUNSET at random. The simple random sampling method is a classical approach to estimate the characteristics of a distribution. The Monte-Carlo method for Simple Random Sampling (SRS) is used. A Wilks formula has been used to determine the number of calculations.

A three uncertain parameters were chosen in this investigation (Table V). The Table V presents reference values of the uncertain parameters used in the basic ASTEC input for the CORDEB2 CP7-02 experiment simulation as well as their probable ranges. The uncertainty of the input parameters is determined from their ranges. It was assumed that the uncertain parameters presented in the Table V could vary in the entire deviation range with the same probability.

Table V. Uncertain parameters

N	Uncertain parameters	Reference value	Deviation range (%)
e1	Power in the melt – (Power)	2.3E + 3 (W)	±20%
e2	Emissivity of the top metal layer – (Emiss)	0.3 (–)	±20%
e3	Species diffusion coefficient – (SDcoef)	0.4E – 9 (m ² /s)	±20%

Using the SUNSET computer tool and ICARE and CESAR modules of ASTECv3.1.1 code, 100 different sets of uncertain input parameters were selected and after that 100 calculations were performed with ASTECv3.1.1.

The uncertainties in three input parameters in the deterministic calculations have been investigated to account their influence on three important output parameters:

- Final mass of the top light metal layer (HM_mass)
- Final mass of the oxide layer (Ox_mass)
- Final mass of the bottom-heavy metal layer (LM_mass)

The presented results in Table VI for the output variables give information about the average values, the standard deviation used to estimate the error due to the uncertainty and the minimal and maximal values summarized from the statistical analysis.

Table VI. Results from classical statistical analysis for the three output parameters

Output variable	Average	Standard deviation	Min	Max
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Output variable #1 (HM_{mass})	0.06183 (kg)	0.043573 (kg)	5.843E – 11 (kg)	0.13326 (kg)
Output variable #2 (Ox_{mass})	1.60948 (kg)	0.004588 (kg)	1.60431 (kg)	1.61181 (kg)
Output variable #3 (LM_{mass})	1.25367 (kg)	0.047922 (kg)	1.17359 (kg)	1.32069 (kg)

For the investigated calculation case sensitivity analyses on the 3 uncertain parameters were performed using the SUNSET computer tool. The Pearson single correlation coefficients, which determined the range of the influence of input parameters on the output parameters are presented in Table VII.

Table VII. Pearson single correlation coefficients for the output parameters

	Output variable #1 (HM_{mass})	Output variable #2 (Ox_{mass})	Output variable #3 (LM_{mass})
e1 (Power)	-0.756809	-0.791492	0.763921
e2 (Emiss)	-0.044266	-0.145343	0.054154
e3 (SDcoef)	-0.529358	-0.356074	0.515416

As it seen from Figure 6 and Table VII increasing of the all input variables lead to intensification of the kinetics in the pool resulting in increasing the mass of top LM layer and decreasing the mass of the bottom HM layer. The most significant influence has the power deposited (input variable #1) in the pool followed by “Species diffusion coefficient” (input variable #3). The influence of the stainless-steel emissivity (input variable #2) is insignificant.

Figure 6. Diagram of Pearson single correlation coefficients for the output variables

5. CONCLUSIONS

During the experiment in the molten pool could be seen stratification in three phases: Oxide phase, light metal phases and phases of heavy metals. The mass of HM in the pool decreases but the mass of LM increases. It means that the species from the heavy metals are assimilated from the oxide layer but the lighter particles move to the top light metal fractions. The ASTEC code predicts this experiment reasonably. During the simulation three layers occurs: LM layer on the top, oxide layer in the middle and HM layer on the bottom. The layer’s masses in the end of ASTECv3.1.1 calculation time (21610 sec) are comparable with the masses accounted from the post-mortem ingot analyses at the end of the

experiment. The mass of the oxide layer calculated by ASTECv3.1.1 is a little bit overestimated (1.61 kg) against the mass of oxide phase at the end of experiment, which is 1.42 kg.

As it seen from the Table IV, there is good agreement between the calculated mass fractions of the species and the experimental mass fractions of the species in the LM layer and in the oxide layer.

Although of the good agreement in the masses of the different phases and in the fractions of the elements in these phases there are significant uncertainties in the kinetics of the species transfer between the phases. Uncertainties in 3 input parameters, which intensified the mass transfer kinetics have been investigated against the final masses of the 3th phases: LM phase, Oxide phase and HM phase. These three input parameters are: "Power in the melt pool", "Emissivity of the LM layer" and "Species diffusion coefficient". The range of deviation of input parameters is chosen to be regular: $\pm 20\%$. After 100 calculations with ASTECv3.1.1 there have been accounted a maximal, an average and a minimal value as well as the standard deviation for the 3 output parameters (final masses of the LM, HM and the Oxide). After that sensitivity calculations have been done with ASTEC/SUNSET to account the range of the influence of input parameters. A Pearson "Single determination coefficients" have been calculated by SUNSET statistical tool. The results show that the higher influence on the intensification of the kinetics of species has increasing of the power inserted in the melt pool. On the second place is increasing of the "Species diffusion coefficient" with single determination coefficients higher than ± 0.5 for the LM and HM masses. Increasing the "Emissivity of the top light metal" influences insignificantly on the output parameters.

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